

ASSESSING TEST CONSTRUCTION AND ADMINISTRATION PRACTICES AMONG LECTURERS OF TERTIARY INSTITUTIONS IN TARABA STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract

This study assessed the test construction knowledge and administration practices among lecturers of tertiary institutions in Taraba State, Nigeria. The study adopted descriptive research design. The population of the study comprised of all academic staff members of tertiary institutions in Taraba State, and a sample of 420 lecturers was drawn using stratified and simple random sampling techniques. Four research questions were raised, and three hypotheses were formulated to guide the study. Data were collected through a researchers' design questionnaire titled Lecturers Test Construction Knowledge and Administration Practices Scale (LTCKAPS). The collected data were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. The findings of this study revealed that the extent of test construction knowledge and administration practices among lecturers of tertiary institutions in Taraba State, Nigeria, is averagely positive. It was also indicated that gender does not significantly influence the test construction knowledge and administration practices of lecturers, but qualification/professionalism significantly influences lecturers' test construction knowledge and administration practices in tertiary institutions in Taraba State, Nigeria. And years of experience do not significantly affect the test construction knowledge and administration practices of lecturers of tertiary institutions in Taraba State, Nigeria. In view of the findings of this study, conclusions were made and it was recommended that government should organize regular seminars and workshop for the lecturers on how to construct valid and reliable tests. Regular evaluation should be put in place by the state government and test and regular evaluation should be put in place by state government, test experts to ensure that reliable and valid tests are developed to have unbiased assessment of students.

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Introduction

Assessment is a process of obtaining information that is used for making decisions about students, curricula and programs, and educational policy. Therefore, it involves the utilization of empirical data on students' learning to improve programs and enhance their learning. The process of gathering evidence about student learning to inform instructional decisions is referred to as assessment (Popham, 2014). It is also the process of gathering, interpreting, and using information about student learning to make informed decisions regarding instruction and student progress. Nitko and Brookhart (2011) stated that not every assessment instrument can elicit the necessary data for assessing learned behaviors. Not every assessment instrument is reliable, and not every graduate or teacher possesses the required skills and competence to design and implement assessment instruments to obtain the desired learning experience. The understanding and application of assessment instruments are critical components of assessment competence.

A test is a standardized procedure for measuring a sample of an individual's behaviour, usually with the aim of making inferences about the individual's characteristics or future behavior.

A test is a method used to determine a student's ability to complete certain tasks or demonstrate mastery of a skill or knowledge of content (Kizlik, 2012). A test is a set of questions that a tester poses to testees to respond to. Therefore, it is a set of questions, tasks, or problems intended to measure an individual's knowledge, intelligence, and other traits.

Aggawal (2007) viewed test as an instrument or systematic procedure for measuring a sample of behavior (how well the individual performs in comparison with others or in comparison with a domain of performance tasks). Therefore, tests measure the correct status of individual intellectual abilities and non-intellectual traits that provide educational and vocational guidance.

Omole, Olatoye, and Adewuni (2025) stated that the importance of tests in the educational system is enormous. The scholars further stated that in the school setting, a test is generally used as an assessment tool for obtaining information about students' learning. Testing is a key component in educational assessment. Tests are used in the classroom to measure students' cognitive ability and knowledge in a particular subject. Kimau (2018), views the purpose of any tests to include the following: ascertaining what students have learned, identifying students' strengths and weaknesses, providing platforms for awards and recognition, and providing ways to measure teachers' and schools' effectiveness.

Tests can either be teacher-made or standardized. When a test is developed and designed by teachers, it is referred to as teacher-made, whereas standardized tests are carefully constructed by public examining bodies or commercial outlets to ensure consistency in the administration, marking, and analysis of test results.

Ugodulunwa (2008) described "teacher-made tests" as tests prepared and used by classroom teachers for specific classes and designed to cover smaller areas of content, knowledge, or skills, whereas Stiggins (2011) saw "teacher-made tests" as oral or written assessments that are not commercially produced and are not standardized. Teacher-made tests are normally administered to students after a period of instruction, if for achievement purposes. Considering the sensitive role that information from a test plays in making educational decisions for students and management, both test developers and users must make conscious effort to improve the validity and reliability of the test to obtain objective information that approximates the individual's true characteristic, which the test developer seeks to estimate.

The National Centre for Assessment in Higher Education (2015) sees test construction as a practical and scientific role that is applied before, during, and after each item until it becomes a part of the test. Test construction is the process of creating a test or assessment instrument that measures a specific construct or domain. This process involves a series of steps, including defining the construct, developing a test blueprint, creating test items, piloting and field-testing the test, and analyzing and interpreting test data. (AERA, APA, and NCME, 2014).

In a dynamic society, educational institutions are constantly concerned with employing competent teachers and instructors who can provide quality academic output, according to Barrientos (2023). In the tertiary institutions of learning, each instructor is expected to quantify how much the students have achieved from a course of instruction. This is done through the administration of tests by the lecturers who may not have adequate knowledge of test construction procedures. Hence, question papers that lack the basic psychometric properties are most often encountered.

According to Inko-Tariah and Okon (2019), the power to assess students rests on the lecturers. One would expect adequate measures to help lecturers acquire the skills in test construction, but this is not the case. Izard (2005) observed that most teacher-made tests mainly assess the lower-level processes as Bloom's taxonomy of educational objectives specified for the cognitive domain.

The quality of the teacher-made test is a matter of concern. Lecturers are expected to possess some requisite skills and competence in the act of test construction as a result of the relevant training they have undergone. The skills acquired by lecturers in test construction will enable them to develop more valid and reliable tests than those without the skills.

Test construction skills include competencies needed for developing quality tests based on the principles of test construction. These competencies are outlined by Agu, Onyekuba, and Anyichie (2013) as follows: objectivity, communication, item validation skills, and skills for applying appropriate strategies to ascertain the reliability of test instruments.

Skills in test construction enable lecturers to construct tests with precision, appropriateness of language use, objectivity, and good grading scales. Silker (2003) explained that teachers need not be experts in educational measurement and evaluation to construct valid and reliable tests, but that every teacher should possess basic test construction skills to construct quality tests. These skills will help teacher's structure items to elicit clear and concise answers from learners, construct tests that are appropriate for learners, and set tests so that students finish within time and do not grow scared of tests. Therefore, lecturers need to apply some acceptable degree of knowledge of test construction to construct valid and reliable tests that will yield accurate feedback of students' achievement.

The most common tests used by lecturers are teacher-made achievement tests, as opposed to standardized tests, which have been established psychometric properties. Ugodunlunwa (2008) believes that the goal of achievement testing is to obtain valid and reliable information about students' achievement that will guide decision making in the school system. To achieve these goals, the test must be carefully planned and constructed. It should be made clear at this point that testing is a key component in educational assessment. For achievement tests, the most important validities to establish are face and content validities. It is also very important to establish the reliability and usability of the tests as achievement tests are a latent trait. All these are incorporated in test construction procedures that each lecturer should be aware of and follow to be able to set good tests.

The difference in academic achievement due to gender differences is crucial to educationists. Gender is the range of physical, mental, and behavioral characteristics pertaining to, and differentiating between, masculinity and femininity. Ololube (2008), who assessed the test construction skills of teachers in Nigeria, found poor test construction skills among non-professional teachers. In the same direction, Hamman-Tukur and Hamafyelto (2015) lamented that teachers' test construction is not encouraging.

Unfortunately, the role of lecturers in test construction and administration practices has been observed as a main source of anxiety, especially with lecturers in tertiary institutions in Taraba State, which largely stems from their inadequate test construction skills. It should be emphasized that most of the lecturers do not have an education background and have never taken a test construction course. A poorly designed test can lead to inaccurate measurement of learning and provide false information about students' performances and instructional

achievement because most teachers fail to acquire knowledge of test construction procedures. This implies the need to assess the teachers' knowledge of test construction in senior secondary schools. Therefore, this study is conceptualized to assess lecturers' test construction knowledge and administration practices in tertiary institutions in Taraba State.

Statement of the problem

The business of teaching and learning is incomplete without an assessment of the students to determine whether the goals are being met. Each lecturer in a university or college is expected to quantify how much their students have learned from a course of instruction. This is usually done by administering tests by a lecturer who may not have sufficient knowledge of test construction procedures, resulting in question papers lacking basic psychometric properties. Being members of a teaching profession, lecturers in the high institution of learning are expected to possess prerequisite knowledge of measurement and evaluation that enables them to construct and administer a good test to their students due to different training they have undergone.

Many studies on the influence of teacher characteristics on test construction knowledge have been conducted by researchers such as Omole, Olatoye and Adewuni (2025), Rufina, Hamman-Tukur, and Stephen (2015), Hamman-Tukur and Rhoda (2017), Adeosun and Mogokwu (2024), Dashe, Obadiah and Falade (2024), Ehigbor and Osumah (2023), Lasisi and Oni (2016), Kinyua and Okunya (2014), and Agu, Onyekuba and Anyichie (2013), but their findings are diversified and inconsistent.

Despite the importance of test construction in an educational system, which should be given due consideration, my personal experience shows that most lecturers in tertiary institutions in Taraba State do not follow the test construction and administering procedures, and this has negative effects on students' performance, which might result in the false assessment of students' achievements.

Teachers' knowledge in test construction has a significant influence the performance of students in the test, either good or bad. Lack of knowledge that enables them to construct valid and reliable tests, which is often considered a cause of failure in examination, is a result of lack of accurate planning, writing, and analysis of relevant test items to be included in the tests.

The quality of most teacher-made tests constructed and used on students in tertiary institutions affects their performance. To improve the quality of teaching, learning, and assessments through assessment, it is necessary to conduct a study to assess the construction knowledge and administration practices of tertiary lecturers across gender, professionalism, and level of teaching experience. This study seeks to assess lecturers' test construction and administration practices in tertiary institutions in Taraba State, Nigeria.

Purpose of the study

The main purpose of this study is to assess the test construction knowledge and administration practices of lecturers in tertiary institutions in Taraba State, Nigeria. Specifically, the study seeks to:

- a. Investigate the extent of the knowledge and administration practices of lecturers in tertiary institutions in Taraba State, Nigeria.
- b. Determine if there is a significant difference in test construction knowledge and administration practices between male and female lecturers in tertiary institutions in Taraba State, Nigeria.
- c. investigate if a significant difference exists in test construction knowledge and Administration practice between professional and unprofessional lecturers in tertiary institutions in Taraba, Nigeria.
- d. Investigate if there is a significant difference in test construction knowledge and administration practices between experienced and less-experienced lecturers in tertiary institutions in Taraba State, Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised to guide the study:

- a. What is the extent of the knowledge and administration practices of lecturers in tertiary institutions in Taraba State, Nigeria?
- b. Is there a significant difference between male and female lecturers in tertiary institutions in Taraba State, Nigeria in terms of test construction knowledge and administration practices?
- c. Is there a significant difference between professional and unprofessional lecturers in tertiary institutions in Taraba State, Nigeria in terms of test construction knowledge and administration practices?
- d. Is there a significant difference between experienced and less-experienced lecturers in tertiary institutions in Taraba State, Nigeria, in test construction knowledge and administration practices?

Research Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at the 0.05 level of significance:

HO¹: No significant difference in test construction knowledge and administration practices between male and female lecturers in tertiary institutions in Taraba State, Nigeria.

HO²: No significant difference in test construction knowledge and administration practices between professional and unprofessional lecturers in tertiary institutions in Taraba State, Nigeria.

HO³: No significant difference in test construction knowledge and administration practices between experienced and less-experienced lecturers in tertiary institutions in Taraba State, Nigeria.

Methodology

This study adopted a descriptive survey research design. This research design allows for the sampling of a large number of respondents; thus, the survey design was considered most appropriate for this study. The study population comprised all teaching staff members of the Tertiary Institution in Taraba State, Nigeria. A total of 420 lecturers were randomly selected using stratified and simple random sampling techniques. Giri (2024) stated that multistage sampling, which is often used in large-scale geographical studies, combines various probability sampling methods for effectiveness and efficiency. It is particularly applicable to extensive inquiries, such as nationwide surveys, to manage complex and diverse populations. The instrument used to collect data in this study was a self-designed questionnaire titled: Lecturers Test Construction Knowledge and Administration Practices Scale (LTCKAPS). The instrument was divided into two sections: A and B. Section: A consists information on bio-data of the respondent such as gender, professionalization, and years of teaching experience (Less experienced = 1 to 10 years, Experienced = 10 and above years). Section B contains 21 items that measure lecturers' knowledge of test construction procedures and administration practices. The questionnaire adopted the Four-Likert response format of VF = Very Frequently of Me, F = Frequently of Me, ST = Sometimes of Me, and N = Never of Me. Four experts in the field of educational tests and measurement validated the quality of the instrument on face and content validity. According to Afemike (2016), reliability is the consistency, dependability, or stability of measures obtained from an assessment. The reliability of the instrument was established through pilot testing with test-retest technique, and the reliability coefficient was found to be 0.69. The instrument was suitable for the study. The researchers visited all the selected tertiary institutions and administered the instruments to the selected respondents. The collected data were analyzed with both descriptive (mean and standard deviation) and inferential (t-test) statistics to answer research question 1 and test the three hypotheses formulated in the study.

Results

Answering of Research Question One: What is the extent of the knowledge and administration practices of lecturers in tertiary institutions in Taraba State, Nigeria?

Table 1: Mean and standard deviation statistics of the extent lecturers of test construction knowledge and administration practices

S/N	Description	Mean	Std. Dev.
1.	Test items are constructed based on the course objectives and	2.61	1.04

	intended learning outcomes.		
2.	I prepare a specification table before developing the test items.	2.85	.95
3.	I ensure that my test items cover various cognitive levels (e.g., knowledge, comprehension, and application).	3.05	.91
4.	I balance the number of questions across all the major topics taught.	2.61	1.04
5.	Avoiding biased or ambiguous language in the test questions.	2.85	.95
6.	I understand the characteristics of a good test (e.g., validity, reliability, and objectivity).	3.17	.82
7.	Different types of questions (e.g., multiple choice, essay, and short answer) are used to assess different skills.	3.05	.91
8.	I provide clear instructions for the participants.	2.63	1.04
9.	I seek peer review or feedback on my test items before administering them.	2.85	.95
10.	I can distinguish between different types of test items and when they should be used.	3.17	.83
11.	I have received formal training on the construction and administration of tests.	2.73	1.08
12.	I ensure a conducive environment for administering tests.	2.85	.95
13.	I consider the item difficulty and discrimination index in the test construction.	2.63	1.04
14.	I closely monitor students to prevent examination misconduct during examinations.	3.05	.91
15.	Test administration is a critical component of the teaching-learning process.	3.04	.92
16.	I document test processes and maintain secure records.	2.73	1.08
17.	I securely handle and store test scripts after examination.	1.70	.76
18.	I accommodate students with special needs or valid excuses.	2.08	.95
19.	I ensure that test administration is conducted in a conducive environment.	2.73	1.08
20.	I ensure that the standard timing is followed during the test administration.	3.23	.80
21.	Reflect on each test administration to improve future practices.	3.05	.911
Cluster mean and standard deviation		2.85	0.95

Table 1 shows the indicators of the extent of the knowledge and administration practices of lecturers in Taraba State. The highest mean knowledge item was “I ensure standard timing is followed during test administration,” with a mean score of 3.23. Other high-level knowledge items included “I can distinguish between different types of test items and when to use them,” and “I ensure that my test items cover various cognitive levels (e.g., knowledge, comprehension, and application).” and “I seek peer review or feedback on my test items before administering them,” with mean scores of 3.17, 3.05, and 2.85, respectively, with standard deviations of 0.80, 0.83, 0.91, and 0.95, respectively. On the other hand, items 17, 18, 1, and 8 had the lowest mean scores of 1.70, 2.80, 2.61, and 2.61, respectively, with standard deviations of 0.76, 0.95, 1.04, and 1.04, respectively.

This implies that the majority of lecturers in tertiary institutions in Taraba State, Nigeria, always use the listed items(1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8, 9, 10, 11, 12,13,14,15,16,19,20, and 21), which were accepted because they had mean

scores above 2.5 of the decision line, while items 17 and 18 were rejected because they had mean scores below 2.5 of the decision line.

Testing of Research Hypothesis

Hypothesis One: No significant difference in test construction knowledge and administration practices between male and female lecturers in tertiary institutions in Taraba State, Nigeria.

Table 2: t-test statistics of knowledge of test construction and practice of test administration among males and females lecturers

Variable	No	Mean	SD	Df	t-value	t-cal. (2 tailed)	Remark
Male	218	39.17	10.131	418	1.027	.100	NS*
Female	202	38.36	9.775				

NS* = Not Significant

Table 2 presents the t-test statistics analysis on the test construction knowledge and administration practices of male and female lecturers in tertiary institutions in Taraba State, Nigeria. The table shows a mean score of 39.17 (standard deviation, 10.131) for male lecturers and a mean score of 38.36 (standard deviation, 9.775) for female lecturers, a degree of freedom (df) of 418, a t-value of 1.027, and a Sig. value (2. tail) of .100 at the 0.05 alpha level of significance. This shows that there is no significant difference between male and female lecturers in the test construction knowledge and administration practices in Taraba State, Nigeria. Therefore, we upheld the null hypothesis one. Thus, there is no significant difference in test construction knowledge and administration practices between male and female lecturers in tertiary institutions in Taraba State, Nigeria. The result implies that gender does not significantly affect the knowledge of lecturers in tertiary institutions in Taraba State, Nigeria, regarding test construction.

Hypothesis Two: No significant difference in test construction knowledge and administration practices Between professional and unprofessional lecturers in tertiary institutions in Taraba State, Nigeria.

Table 3: t-test statistics of knowledge of test construction and administration practice of professional and unprofessional lecturers

Variable	No	Mean	SD	Df	t-value	t-cal. (2 tailed)	Remark
Professional	197	40.54	10.841	418	2.058	.000	S*
Non-Professional	223	36.28	8.240				

Sig.* = Significant

Table 3 presents the t-test statistics analysis on the test construction knowledge and administration practices of professional and unprofessional lecturers in tertiary institutions in Taraba State, Nigeria. The table shows a mean score of 40.54, standard deviation of 10.841, mean score of 36.28, standard deviation of 8.240, degree of freedom (df) of 418, t-value of 2.058, and Sig. Value (2. tail) of .000 at the 0.05 alpha level of significance. The above result also indicates a significant difference between the mean scores of non-professionals and non-professionals lecturers' test construction knowledge in tertiary institutions in Taraba State, Nigeria. The result implies that qualification/professionalism significantly affects the test construction knowledge of lecturers in tertiary institutions in Taraba State, Nigeria.

Hypothesis Three: No significant difference in test construction knowledge and administration practices between experienced and less-experienced lecturers in tertiary institutions in Taraba State, Nigeria.

Table 4: t-test statistics of knowledge of test construction and administration practice of experienced and less experienced lecturers.

Variable	No	Mean	SD	Df	t-value	t-cal. (2 tailed)	Remark
Experienced	315	37.192	10.152	418	.274	.145	NS*
Less experienced	105	36.475	9.225				

NS* = Not Significant

Table 4 presents the t-test statistics analysis on the test construction knowledge and administration practices of experienced and less-experienced lecturers in tertiary institutions in Taraba State, Nigeria. The table shows the mean score of 37.192, standard deviation of 10.152 for experienced teachers and mean score of 36.475, standard deviation of 9.225 for less experienced teachers, df of 418, t-value of .274, and sig. (2. tailed) of .145 at the 0.05 alpha level of significance. The table also shows 315 experienced lecturers and 105 less experienced lecturers of 105. This reveals that more experienced lecturers are employed than less experienced lecturers in basic schools in tertiary institutions in Taraba State, Nigeria. The above result also indicates that there is no significant difference between the mean scores of experienced and less experienced teachers' test construction knowledge in basic schools in Taraba State, Nigeria. Therefore, hypothesis three was accepted. Thus, there is no significant difference in test construction knowledge and administration practices between experienced and less experienced lecturers in tertiary institutions in Taraba State, Nigeria. This result implies that teaching experience does not have a significant influence on the knowledge and administration practices of lecturers in tertiary institutions in Taraba State, Nigeria.

Discussion of the Findings

This study assessed the test construction knowledge and administration practices of lecturers in tertiary institutions in Taraba State, Nigeria. Findings on the common test construction knowledge and administration practices indicated that the highest mean knowledge is the item that says, "I ensure standard timing is followed during test administration." with a mean score of 3.23 Other knowledge that has a high score on the table include the knowledge that says, "I can distinguish between different types of test items and when to use them.", "I ensure that my test items cover various cognitive levels (e.g., knowledge, comprehension, and application)." and "I seek peer review or feedback on my test items before administering them," with mean scores of 3.17, 3.05, and 2.85, respectively, with standard deviations of 0.80, 0.83, 0.91, and 0.95, respectively. On the other hand, items 17, 18, 1, and 8 had the lowest mean scores of 1.70, 2.80, 2.61, and 2.61, respectively, with standard deviations of 0.76, 0.95, 1.04, and 1.04, respectively.

These findings showed that lecturers in tertiary institutions in Taraba State, Nigeria, ensure that standard timing is followed during test administration. I can distinguish between different types of test items and when to use them. I also ensure that my test items cover various cognitive levels. I seek peer review or feedback on my test items before administering them. However, they are relatively low in item I, handle and store test scripts securely after examination and accommodate students with special needs or valid excuses.

The first hypothesis states that there is no significant difference in test construction knowledge and administration practices between male and female lecturers in tertiary institutions in Taraba State, Nigeria. The findings of this study indicated that gender does not significantly affect the knowledge and administration practices of lecturers in tertiary institutions in Taraba State, Nigeria. This finding corroborates the findings of Omole, Olatoye, and Adewuni (2025), Dashe, Obadijah, and Falade (2024), Ahmed, Abdullahi, and Bashir (2022), and Okon (2014). Omole, Olatoye, and Adewuni (2025) confirmed that gender does not significantly affect the test construction knowledge of basic school teachers in Lokoja metropolis, Kogi State, Nigeria. Dashe, Obadijah, and Falade (2024) reported that gender is not significant in the knowledge and procedures employed in the construction of classroom achievement test. Ahmed, Abdullahi, and Bashir (2022) reported no significant gender difference in test construction competency among teachers of JSS in Jigawa State. This is

probably because both male and female teachers undergo the same training as the students. However, this finding contradicts the findings of Adeosun and Mogokwu (2024), Ehigbor and Osumah (2023), and Camble and Hamman-Tukur (2017). Adeosun and Mogokwu (2024) reported that a significant difference exists among the teachers in the area of competency in test construction based on sex, Ehigbor and Osumah (2023) stated that female teachers had higher level of multiple-choice construction competencies than male teachers in secondary schools in the district, and Camble and Hamman-Tukur (2017) established the relationship between teachers' knowledge of test construction and gender.

The second hypothesis states that there is no significant difference in test construction knowledge and administration practices between professional and unprofessional lecturers in Taraba State, Nigeria. This study revealed that qualification/professionalism significantly affects the test construction knowledge of lecturers in tertiary institutions in Taraba State, Nigeria. This finding supports the findings of Dashe, Obadiah, and Falade (2024), Sani, Usamatu, and Muhammad (2024), and Salihu (2019). Dashe, Obadiah, and Falade (2024) reported that qualification has an impact on the knowledge of test construction procedures, while Sani, Usamatu, and Muhammad (2024) showed that there is a significant difference in test construction competency among professional and non-professional lecturers of JSS in Jigawa State. Salihu (2019) revealed that there was a significant mean difference in ability in test construction between professional and non-professional teachers of Economics. However, Omole, Olatoye, and Adewuni (2025), Adeosun and Mogokwu (2024), and Lasisi and Oni (2016). Omole, Olatoye, and Adewuni (2025) reported that qualification/professionalism significantly affects the knowledge and administration practices of tertiary lecturers in Taraba State, Nigeria. Adeosun and Mogokwu (2024) stated that no significant differences were found among the teachers' competency in test construction based on qualification. Lasisi and Oni (2016) also found no significant difference in the learning assessment competence of teachers based on their level of qualification.

The third hypothesis states that there is no significant difference in the knowledge and administration practices of lecturers in tertiary institutions in Taraba State, Nigeria. The findings of this study indicate that teaching experience does not have a significant influence on the knowledge and administration practices of lecturers in tertiary institutions in Taraba State, Nigeria. This finding supports the findings of Omole, Olatoye, and Adewuni (2025), Adeosun and Mogokwu (2024), and Lasisi and Oni (2016) and Agu, Onyekuba, and Anyichie (2013). Omole, Olatoye, and Adewuni (2025) stated that there is no significant difference in the test construction knowledge of experienced and less experienced basic school teachers in Lokoja metropolis, Kogi State, Nigeria. Adeosun and Mogokwu (2024) confirmed that no significant differences were found among the teachers' competency in test construction based on years of experience, whereas Lasisi and Oni (2016) reported no significant difference in learning assessment competence of teachers based on their year of experience. Agu, Onyekuba, and Anyichie (2013) reported no significant difference in the mean ratings of experienced and less experienced teachers regarding their competences in constructing classroom base tests. However, the findings of Dashe, Obadiah, and Falade (2024) and Kinyua and Okunya (2014) were not consistent. Dashe, Obadiah, and Falade (2024) confirmed that years of teaching experience have an impact on the knowledge of test construction procedures, while Kinyua and Okunya (2014) claimed that teachers' experience varies with the number of years they have been teaching and that the experience of teachers affects the validity of a test more than its reliability.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of this study, it was concluded that items that say, "I ensure standard timing is followed during test administration" are the most common factor, while the items that say "I handle and store test scripts securely after examination" are the least common. Gender and teaching experience do not significantly affect the knowledge and administration practices of lecturers in tertiary institutions in Taraba State, Nigeria.

However, qualification/professionalism significantly influences the knowledge and administration practices of lecturers in tertiary institutions in Taraba State, Nigeria.

Recommendations

In view of the findings and conclusions of this study, the following recommendations were made:

- i. Workshops on test construction and administration practices should be organized to improve the ability of lecturers to construct valid tests.
- ii. The government should organize frequent seminars and workshops for lecturers on how to construct valid and reliable test items.
- iii. Regular evaluation should most be put in place by state government test experts to ensure that reliable and valid tests are developed to have unbiased assessment of students.

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